

Range Of Gravitational Force and Gravitons

Somnath Chakraborty

Khano High School

Mail: somnathphy@gmail.com

Mb:919432889711

Abstract : Gravitational force is the most common force in nature. Gravitational force appears in between any two objects(masses). Now, our object is to find the range of gravitational interaction between two objects. The range of gravitational interaction is not infinite but finite.

Keywords: Gravitational force, mass defect, range of gravitational force.

Explanation: the origin of gravitational energy is mass defect of interacting objects[1]. This mass defect is converted into gravitational energy according to Einstein equation $E=mc^2$. This mass defect of interacting objects or particles depend on the masses of the objects or particles and the distance between them[2].This missing mass(mass defect) during the interaction distributed over the quanta of gravitational force i.e Graviton. If in a gravitational interaction there is a mass defect of a amount Δm and the numbers of involving graviton is N then we must need $\Delta m=Nm$. Where m is the fundamental mass of Graviton. There is no fractional mass of Graviton mass(m). So, for gravitational interaction we must need at least one Graviton i.e mass defect must be equal or greater than the mass of a single Graviton [$\Delta m \geq m$].

The equation for mass defect for two interacting objects having masses $M(1),M(2)$ is

$$\Delta m= GM(1)M(2)/rc^2 \quad [2] \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where c is the velocity of light in free space and r is the distance between the objects. If for a certain distance λ ,the mass defect in the interaction between

M(1) and M(2) become m i.e mass of a single graviton then λ is the range of the gravitational interaction for these two objects.

From equation 1

$$m = GM(1)M(2)/\lambda c^2$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda = GM(1)M(2)/mc^2$$

so, range of gravitational force depends on the masses of the interacting objects or particles. Masses of interacting particles cannot be infinite. So, range of gravitational interaction is finite.

References:

[1] <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2619297>

[2] <http://www.ijnrd.org/papers/IJNRD1902001.pdf>